

Distribution and abundance of Soil-algae in Rice-fields Ecosystem of South Kamrup District of Assam

Paper Id : 20500 Submission Date : 2025-07-27 Acceptance Date : 2025-08-06 Publication Date : 2025-08-10

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16882902

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/researchtimes.php#8>

Kamal Choudhury

Assistant Professor
Botany
SBMS College
Sualkuchi, Assam, India

Sikha Rani Kalita

Assistant Professor
Zoology
SBMS College
Sualkuchi, Assam, India

Abstract

The rice-field ecosystem provides a favourable environment for the growth of algae with respect to their requirement of light, water, temperature and nutrient availability. Algae play an important role in maintenance and build-up of soil fertility, consequently increase rice growth and yield as a natural biofertilizer. Present study was carried out during the year 2023 -24 and deals with the study of distribution and abundance of rice-field algae of Kamrup district, Assam. The study sites of rice fields were selected from four village of South Kamrup district (rural) of Assam. Altogether 45 algal species belonging to 24 genera under Cyanophyceae, Chlorophyceae, Bacillariophyceae were identified. On the basis of abundance, the Cyanophyceae was the dominant group followed by Chlorophyceae and Bacillariophyceae. The seasonal percentages of Relative abundance for Cyanophyceae ranged between 5.377% (Winter) to 31.692% (Monsoon); Chlorophyceae 2.957% (Winter) to 14.161% (Monsoon) and Bacillariophyceae from 0.888% (Post-monsoon) to 3.589% (Monsoon). The Class Cyanophyceae shows maximum abundance followed by Chlorophyceae and Bacillariophyceae.

Keywords

Algae, Rice-field, Distribution, Abundance.

Introduction

The floristic pattern and ecology of soil algae is of prime importance to understand the problem created on account of population. Though the study of soil algae is of a much demanding than that of aquatic component but the ecology of soil algae has been much less studies in comparison to that of heterotrophic soil microorganisms (Foog, *et al*, 1973; Schubert, 1984). In rice-fields harbours variety of biological organisms including algae and other macrophytes. Species of Cyanobacteria played a vital role to enrich the productivity of paddy crops in India (Singh, 1961; Chowdhary *et al*, 2011). Information on algal diversity is important to understand the factors influencing rise and fall, change in algal populations, interaction of algae with other organisms (Round, 1981; Kumar, 1999). The importances of algal dynamics, particularly their response to environmental changes have been suggested in several studies (Starks *et al*, 1981; Pandey, *et al*, 1998).

Objective of study

The present study was undertaken with following aim and objectives:

1. To isolate and identify the algal forms from the rice-fields of Kamrup district of Assam
2. To study the variation of algal flora in four different collected sites of four villages rice-fields of Kamrup district, Assam along with their seasonal changes.

Review of Literature

1. Ahmed and Kalita (2001) worked on Distributional Pattern of Cyanobacteria in Nagoan Sub-division of Nagaon district, Assam.
2. Bharadwaj and Baruah (2013) studied in diversity and abundance of nitrogen-fixing Cyanobacteria population in rice field soil crusts of Lower Brahmaputra Valley agroclimatic zone.
3. Dasgupta and Ahmed (2013) studied on potential rice field BGA isolates from Sonitpur district Assam.
4. Alam *et al.*, (2014) studied on Role of Blue Green Algae in Paddy Crop. They found the better efficiency of cyanobacteria in promoting the growth of rice plants in soil.
5. Sandhyarani and Kumar (2014), worked on distribution of Blue-green Algae in Rice-fields of Warangal District of Andhra Pradesh, India.
6. Singh, *et al.*, (2015) worked on Distribution of Blue-green Algae in Rice-fields of Varanasi and they conclude that Cyanobacteria play an important role in maintenance and build-up of soil fertility.
7. Narasimha Rao *et al.*, (2021) reported 62 algal species belonging to four major classes of algae -Cyanophyceae, Chlorophyceae, Euglenophyceae and Bacillariophyceae from Paddy fields of Razole Mandal, East Godavari district, Andhra Pradesh.

8. Gaikwad (2022) studied on Algal Diversity in Paddy Fields of Bhor and Velhe Talukas of Pune District Maharashtra State, India and reported 20 Algae were found in rice fields. Jagtap, *et al.*, (2025). Studied on soil algae from Sugarcane crop field of Tehsil Indapur, Dist.-Pune, Maharashtra.

Methodology

Site selection: Sites were selected in four village of South Kamrup district (rural) of Assam. These were **Site-1** (Majkuchi village); **Site-2** (Amranga village), **Site-3** (Sikarhati village) and **Site-4** (Tatibama village). In each village, rice fields were used as sampling sites.

Collection of Soil Samples and raise of Enrichment culture:

The samples soil collections were done during the study periods in all the four climatic seasons from rice-fields in the selected sampling sites (S-1, S-2, S-3 and S-4) of South Kamrup district of Assam. Enrichment cultures were raised in Bold Basal Medium (Nichols and Bold 1965) with pH adjusted to 7. The cultures were maintained under light intensity of 2500 lux at a daily cycle of 16 hour of light and 8 hours of darkness and temperature was maintained in between 25-28° C (Singh *et. al.*, 2015).

Analysis

The microscopic analysis of algal forms was done following the keys given by Smith (1950); Prescott (1951); Desikachary (1959); Anand (1989); Bellingier and Sigee 2010.

Quantitative Analysis of Algal forms

For numerical analysis 1 drop (0.03 ml) of culture taken on a glass slide and covered with simple cover-slip and subjected for microscopic field to count the algal forms. The numerical counting of the algal forms per microscopic field was done following Lacky's (1938) drop count method, and the total populations of the algal forms were calculated.

Relative Abundance (RA) of each species in each season was estimate using the following formula:

$$RA = n/N \times 100$$

Where,

n = Number of cells per species.

N = Total number of cells present.

Result and Discussion

Altogether 45 algal species belonging 24 genera under 3 classes - Cyanophyceae, Chlorophyceae, Bacillariophyceae were recorded. At community level Cyanophyceae was the dominant group represented by 28 species followed by Chlorophyceae (12) and Bacillariophyceae (5). The maximum numbers of species were observed during Monsoon season followed by Pre-monsoon, post-monsoon, and winter seasons.

All the investigating results of the seasonal studies have given in Table 1a & 1b and the data obtained from numerical calculations are plotted in Table 2 & 3. While all these are described, based on different collection sites of the rice-fields are follows:

Table 1a: Seasonal variations of algal species at different collection sites of rice-fields (Site -1 & Site -2)

S. No.	Name of Species	Class	Site -1				Site -2			
			W	Pr-M	M	Po-M	W	Pr-M	M	Po-M
1	Chroococcus minor	Cyanophyceae	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
2	Gleocapsa alpicola	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
3	G. rupestris	-do-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
4	Aphanocapsa pulchra	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-
5	A. banarensis	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
6	Oscillatoria chlorine	-do-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
7	O. salina	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
8	O. tenuis	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
9	O. willei	-do-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
10	Phormidium autumnale	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
11	P. fragile	-do-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
12	P. uncinatum	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
13	Lyngbya aeruginocoerulea	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-
14	L. contorta	-do-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
15	L. majuscula	-do-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-
16	Nostoc commune	-do-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	+
17	N. linckia	-do-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
18	N. muscorum	-do-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-
19	N. spongiaeforme	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
20	Anabaena doliolum	-do-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
21	A. fertilissima	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
22	Aulosira prolifica	-do-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-
23	Plactonema notatum	-do-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
24	Scytonema hofmanni	-do-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	-
25	S. schmidtii	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
26	Tolypothrix tenuis	-do-	-	-	-	+	-	+	+	-
27	Haplosiphon fontinalis	-do-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-
28	Westiellopsis prolifica	-do-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+
29	Chlorococcum humicola	Chlorophyceae	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
30	C. diplobonticum	-do-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
31	Chlorela vulgaris	-do-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	+
32	Scendesmus acuminatus	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
33	S. dimorphus	-do-	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	+
34	Ulothrix moniliformis	-do-	-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-
35	Ulothrix zonata	-do-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-
36	Stigeoclonium attenuatum	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
37	S. tenue	-do-	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
38	Vaucheria sessilis	-do-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+
39	Closterium diane	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
40	C. lanceolatum	-do-	+	-	-	-	+	+	+	-
41	Navicula rhynchocephala	Bacillariophyceae	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
42	Nvicula sp.	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+	-
43	Fragilaria brevisstrita	-do-	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	-
44	F. capuciana	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
45	Tabellaria fenestrata	-do-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-

Table 1b: Seasonal variations of algal species at different collection sites of rice-fields (Site -3 & Site -4)

S. No.	Name of Species	Class	Site -1				Site -2			
			W	Pr-M	M	Po-M	W	Pr-M	M	Po-M
1	Chroococcus minor	Cyanophyceae	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
2	Gleocapsa alpicola	-do-	-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+
3	G. rupestris	-do-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
4	Aphanocapsa pulchra	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
5	A. banarensis	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
6	Oscillatoria chlorine	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
7	O. salina	-do-	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
8	O. tenuis	-do-	-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+
9	O. willei	-do-	+	+	+	-	-	-	+	-
10	Phormidium autumnale	-do-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	-
11	P. fragile	-do-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
12	P. uncinatum	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
13	Lyngbya aeruginosa	-do-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
14	L. contorta	-do-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-
15	L. majuscula	-do-	-	-	+	+	+	+	+	-
16	Nostoc commune	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-
17	N. linckia	-do-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+
18	N. muscorum	-do-	+	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
19	N. spongiaeforme	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
20	Anabaena doliolum	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
21	A. fertilissima	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
22	Aulosira prolifica	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
23	Plactonema notatum	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
24	Scytonema hofmanni	-do-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-
25	S. schmidtii	-do-	-	-	+	-	-	+	+	-
26	Tolypothrix tenuis	-do-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	-
27	Haplosiphon fontinalis	-do-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
28	Westiellopsis prolifica	-do-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-
29	Chlorococcus humicola	Chlorophyceae	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
30	C. diplobionticum	-do-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-
31	Chlorella vulgaris	-do-	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+
32	Scendesmus acuminatus	-do-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-
33	S. dimorphus	-do-	-	-	+	+	-	+	+	+
34	Ulothrix moniliformis	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
35	Ulothrix zonata	-do-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-
36	Stigeoclonium attenuatum	-do-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
37	S. tenue	-do-	+	+	+	-	-	+	+	+
38	Vaucheria sessilis	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
39	Closterium diane	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
40	C. lanceolatum	-do-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-
41	Navicula rhynchocephala	Bacillariophyceae	-	+	+	-	-	-	+	+
42	Nvicula sp.	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
43	Fragilaria brevistrita	-do-	-	-	-	-	+	+	+	-
44	F. capuciana	-do-	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-
45	Tabellaria fenestrata	-do-	-	+	+	+	-	-	-	-

+ = present; - = absent W = Winter; Pr-M = Pre-monsoon; M = Monsoon; Po-M = post-monsoon

Study Site -1 (S-1):

A total 28 numbers of algal species were observed out of which 16 belongs to Cyanophyceae, 9 belongs to Chlorophyceae and 3 from Bacillariophyceae.

The algal populations show marked variation in different seasons. Higher numbers of species were observed in Monsoon season (25) followed by Pre-monsoon (16), Retreating-monsoon (13) and Winter (10). The species Nostoc linckia and Navicula rhynchocephala were observed in all the four seasons while the species like Chroococcus minor, Oscillatoria chlorine, Nostoc commune, Chlorella vulgaris were observed only in Monsoon, Tolypothrix tenuis in Post-monsoon and Closterium lanceolatum in Winter season only.

The seasonal relative abundance percentage for Cyanophyceae varies from 4.747% (Winter) to 32.436% (Monsoon); Chlorophyceae 3.956% (Winter) to 14.873% (Monsoon) and Bacillariophyceae from 1.266 % (Winter) to 4.272% (Monsoon).

Study Site -2 (S-2):

Here total 27 numbers of species were observed out of which 17 species from Cyanophyceae; 7 from Chlorophyceae and 3 from Bacillariophyceae.

The algal populations show marked variation in different seasons. Higher numbers of species were observed in Monsoon season (22) followed by Pre-monsoon (14), Post-monsoon (12) and Winter (9). The species like Gleocapsa rupestris, Oscillatoria willei, were appeared in all the four climatic seasons while the species like Aphanocapsa

banaresensis, Oscillatoria salina, Scytonema hofmanni were appeared only in Monsoon season; Aulosira prolifica, Ulothrix moniliformis and Fragilaria brevistrita in Winter and Closterium diane in Pre-monsoon and Nostoc commune observed in Post-monsoon only.

The seasonal percentages (relative abundance) for Cyanophyceae ranged between 6.219% (Winter) to 30.604% (Monsoon); Chlorophyceae 2.291% (Winter) to 12.766% (Monsoon) and Bacillariophyceae from 1.146% (Winter) to 2.455% (Monsoon).

Table 2: Relative abundance (%) of algal genera in different rice-fields of the study sites.

S. No.	Name of Algal Genera	Class	Seasons	S-1	S-2	S-3	S-4
1	Chroococcus	Cyanophyceae	W	-	-	-	-
			Pre-M	-	-	-	-
			M	5.538	-	-	4.714
			Po-M	-	-	-	-
2	Gleocapsa	-do-	W	-	2.946	-	1.857
			Pre-M	-	4.419	4.589	3.143
			M	4.272	4.092	6.501	5.714
			Po-M	3.956	2.455	4.206	2.429
3	Aphanocapsa	-do-	W	-	-	-	-
			Pre-M	-	3.109	-	-
			M	-	3.273	-	5.00
			Po-M	-	-	-	2.00
4	Oscillatoria	-do-	W	0.791	0.818	1.147	1.286
			Pre-M	1.108	1.146	1.912	2.285
			M	3.797	3.601	3.633	4.857
			Po-M	-	2.128	2.486	2.143
5	Phormidium	-do-	W	-	-	-	-
			Pre-M	-	-	1.53	-
			M	3.006	2.618	3.059	2.286
			Po-M	1.899	2.291	1.147	1.143
6	Lyngbya	-do-	W	0.633	-	0.956	1.429
			Pre-M	2.532	1.473	2.103	2.143
			M	3.323	2.782	3.824	3.714
			Po-M	1.582	-	1.721	-
7	Nostoc	-do-	W	2.532	1.146	1.530	-
			Pre-M	2.848	2.946	2.294	2.429
			M	6.487	5.892	4.971	4.286
			Po-M	3.006	4.583	2.103	2.286
8	Anabaena	-do-	W	-	-	-	-
			Pre-M	1.108	-	-	-
			M	1.266	1.800	-	-
			Po-M	0.791	1.473	-	-
9	Aulosira	-do-	W	-	0.491	-	-
			Pre-M	-	-	-	-
			M	-	-	-	-
			Po-M	-	-	-	-
10	Plectonema	-do-	W	-	-	-	-
			Pre-M	0.791	-	-	0.571
			M	0.949	-	-	1.286
			Po-M	-	-	-	-
11	Scytonema	-do-	W	-	-	-	-
			Pre-M	-	-	-	-
			M	0.633	1.473	1.338	1.00
			Po-M	0.316	-	-	-
12	Tolypothrix	-do-	W	-	-	0.765	0.428
			Pre-M	-	1.146	1.338	1.143
			M	-	1.800	2.103	1.429
			Po-M	1.741	-	-	-
13	Haplosiphon	-do-	W	0.791	0.818	-	-
			Pre-M	0.791	1.309	-	-
			M	1.899	1.964	1.530	-
			Po-M	-	-	2.294	-
14	Westolopsis	-do-	W	-	-	1.147	-
			Pre-M	0.949	-	1.721	-
			M	1.266	1.309	2.486	-
			Po-M	-	1.473	-	-
15	Chlorococcum	Chlorophyceae	W	1.108	-	-	-
			Pre-M	3.165	-	1.721	1.857
			M	7.120	-	4.015	2.571
			Po-M	1.108	-	5.163	5.571
16	Chlorella	-do-	W	-	-	-	2.00

			Pre-M	-	1.964	-	-
			M	1.740	6.547	2.294	-
			Po-M	-	3.437	3.250	2.571
17	Scandesmus	-do-	W	1.108	-	-	1.286
			Pre-M	1.108	-	-	-
			M	1.424	1.473	-	1.286
			Po-M	-	1.146	1.721	2.429
18	Ulothrix	-do-	W	-	1.637	2.486	1.428
			Pre-M	-	0.982	-	-
			M	1.582	1.309	-	-
			Po-M	1.424	-	1.53	-
19	Stigeoclonium	-do-	W	0.791	-	1.147	-
			Pre-M	1.740	-	1.147	-
			M	1.899	-	1.530	1.00
			Po-M	1.582	-	2.486	1.429
20	Vaucheria	-do-	W	-	-	-	1.143
			Pre-M	0.633	-	-	-
			M	1.108	0.818	-	-
			Po-M	-	0.655	-	-
21	Closterium	-do-	W	0.949	0.654	-	0.857
			Pre-M	-	2.782	-	1.571
			M	-	2.619	-	2.857
			Po-M	-	-	-	-
22	Fragilaria	Bacillariophyceae	W	-	1.146	-	1.143
			Pre-M	1.108	-	-	2.429
			M	1.424	-	-	3.143
			Po-M	-	-	-	-
23	Tabellaria	-do-	W	-	-	-	-
			Pre-M	-	-	0.956	-
			M	0.791	-	1.147	-
			Po-M	0.633	-	1.338	-
24	Navicula	-do-	W	1.266	-	-	-
			Pre-M	0.791	2.128	1.721	-
			M	2.057	2.455	1.912	1.428
			Po-M	1.740	1.472	-	1.00

S-1 = Site-1; S-2 =Site-2; S-3 = Site-3; S-4= Site -4

W = Winter; Pre-M =Pre-monsoon; M = Monsoon; Po-M = post-monsoon

Study Site -3 (S-3):

This Site was also characterized by the existence of the three major algal groups. All total 25 number of species were recorded of which 16 species belong to Cyanophyceae; 7 belongs to Chlorophyceae and 2 species belongs to Bacillariophyceae.

Higher numbers of species were observed in Monsoon season (23) followed by Pre-monsoon (14), post-monsoon (13) and Winter (7). The species like *Lyngbya contorta*, *Nostoc muscorum* were appeared in all the four climatic seasons while the species like *Lyngbya aerugineo-coerulea*, *Nostoc linckia*, *Scytonema scimiditii*, *Stigeoclonium attenuatum* were observed only in Monsoon season and *Oscillatoria tenuis* and *Scendesmus acuminatus* observed in Post-monsoon only.

The Relative abundance percentage of Cyanophyceae was fluctuates between the range of 5.545% of Winter and 29.445% of Monsoon; Chlorophyceae from 2.868% of Winter to 14.149% of Monsoon and Bacillariophyceae from 0% of Winter to 3.059% of Pre-monsoon.

Table 3: Class wise total Relative abundance (%) of Algal taxa

Algal Class	Season	Site- 1	Site -2	Site-3	Site -4
Cyanophyceae	Winter	4.747	6.219	5.545	5.00
	Pre-monsoon	10.127	15.548	15.487	11.714
	Monsoon	32.436	30.604	29.445	34.286
	Post-monsoon	13.291	14.403	13.957	10.00
Chlorophyceae	Winter	3.956	2.291	2.868	2.714
	Pre-monsoon	6.646	5.728	7.839	6.428
	Monsoon	14.873	12.766	14.150	14.857
	Post-monsoon	4.114	5.238	3.633	5.857
Bacillariophyceae	Winter	1.266	1.146	0	1.143
	Pre-monsoon	1.899	2.128	2.677	2.429
	Monsoon	4.272	2.455	3.059	4.571
	Post-monsoon	2.373	1.472	1.338	1.00

Study Site -4 (S- 4):

All total 30 number of species were observed out of which 20 species belong to Cyanophyceae; 7 species belong to Chlorophyceae and 3 species belong to Bacillariophyceae.

As other sites higher numbers of species were observed in Monsoon season (27) followed by Pre-monsoon (16), post-monsoon (14) and Winter (10). The species like *Gleocapsa rupestris*, *Oscillatoria salina*, *O. tenuis*, *Chlorococcum humicola* were appeared in all the four climatic seasons while the species like *Chrococcus minor*, *Phormidium autumnale*, *Scytonema hofamanni* were appeared only in Monsoon season; *Nostoc commune* and *Closterium diane* in Pre-monsoon and *Nostoc linckia* restricted to Post-monsoon only.

The seasonal percentages (relative abundance) for Cyanophyceae ranged between 5.00% (Winter) to 34.286% (Monsoon); Chlorophyceae 2.714% (Winter) to 14.857% (Monsoon) and Bacillariophyceae from 1.00% (Post-monsoon) to 4.571% (Monsoon).

Discussion

The availability of algal forms varies seasonally in different study sites (S-1, S-2, S-3 and S-4). Some species were common to all the Sites and seasons and on the other hand some were restricted to certain collection site or season only.

The species like *Gleocapsa rupestris*, *Oscillatoria willei*, *Nostoc linckia*, *N. muscorum*, *Tolypothrix tenuis*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Scenedesmus dimorphus*, *Navicula rhyngocephala* were observed from all the four collection sites. On the other hand, some species were restricted to one site only, which were *Nostoc spongiaeforme* (S-4), *Anabaena doliolum* (S-1), *A. fertilissima* (S-2), *Aulosira prolifica* (S-2), *Scytonema schmidtii* (S-3); *Scenedesmus acuminatus* (S-3), *Stigeoclonium attenuatum* (S-3), *Closterium diane* (S-2), *Navicula sp.* (S-2) and *Fragilaria capuciana* (S-4).

Similarly certain species were restricted to one season only namely: *Chrococcus minor* (Monsoon), *Oscillatoria chlorina* (Monsoon), *Aulosira prolifica* (Winter), *Scytonema schmidtii* (Monsoon), *Scenedesmus acuminatus* (Retreating-monsoon), *Stigeoclonium attenuatum* (Monsoon), *Closterium diane* (Pre-monsoon), *Fragilaria capuciana* (Monsoon).

In the study, the maximum and minimum relative abundance percentage in Cyanophyceae varies between the range of 4.747% (S-1) and 34.286% (S-4); in Chlorophyceae between 2.714% (S-4) and 14.873% (S-1) and Bacillariophyceae 0 % (S-3) and 4.571% in S-4 (Table 2 & 3)

Conclusion

Blue-green algae are reported to contribute to the higher nitrogen fertility of rice fields. They grow on the surface of paddy soil with good source of nitrogen. In the present investigation in case of abundance the Class Cyanophyceae shows maximum abundance followed by Chlorophyceae and Bacillariophyceae with relative abundance value (average) 63.202%, 28.489% and 13.017% respectively, which indicates the abundance of nitrogen-fixing blue-green algae in the present study area. Nitrogen fixing blue-green algae reported in this observation are *Nostoc*, *Anabaena*, *Aulosira*, *Lyngbya*, *Oscillatoria*, *Scytonema*, *Tolypothrix*, *Haplosiphon* and *Westolopsis*. The availability of more nitrogen -fixing Cyanophycean algae helps to reduce the use of chemical fertilizer.

References

1. Ahmed, S.U. and Kalita, M.C. (2001). *Distributional Pattern of Cyanobacteria in Nagoan Sub-division, Nagaon, Assam. Three Decades of Research in Biofertilizers and Organic Farming in North East India. Ed. Yadav and Raychoudhury. 84-90*
2. Anand, N. (1989). *Handbook of Blue-green Algae of Rice-fields of South India. Publ. Bishan Singh and Mahendra Pal Singh, Dehradun, p. 80.*

3. Alam, S. Seth, R.K. and Shukla, D.N. (2014). Role of Blue Green Algae in Paddy Crop. *European Journal of Experimental Biology*. 4(5):24-28.
4. Bellinger, E. and Sigee, D. D. (2010). *Freshwater Algae: Identification and Use as Bioindicators*. ISBN: 978-0-470-05814-5. 284 pp.
5. Bharadwaj, N., and Baruah, P. P. (2013). Diversity and abundance of N₂ fixing Cyanobacteria population in rice field soil crusts of Lower Brahmaputra Valley agroclimatic zone. *J. Algal Biomass Utln*. 4(4): 23-33.
6. Choudhary, K.K. (2011). Occurrence of nitrogen fixing cyanobacteria during different stages of paddy cultivation. *Bangladesh J. Plant Taxon*. 18(1):73-76.
7. Dasgupta, M. and Ahmed, S.U. (2013). Some potential rice field BGA isolates from Sonitpur district Assam, North east India. *J. Nat. Prod. Plant Resour*. 3(4): 17-23.
8. Desikachary, T.V. (1959). *Cyanophyta*. Indian Council of Agricultural Research, New Delhi.
9. Fogg G.E. Stewart, W.D.P. Fay, P. and Wesley, A.E. (1973). *The Blue-green Algae*. Academic press, London and New York.
10. Gaikwad, S.A. (2022). Algal Diversity in Paddy Fields of Bhor and Velhe. Talukas of Pune District Maharashtra State, India. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR)*. 4(5): 1-7.
11. Jagtap, A.J., Chavan, S.J. and Chitale, R.D. (2025). Studies on soil algae from Sugarcane crop field of Tehsil Indapur, Dist.-Pune, Maharashtra. *International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology*. 11(11): 241-243.
12. Kumar, H.D. (1999). *Introductory phycology*. Affiliated East and West Press Pvt. Ltd.
13. Lacky, J.B. (1938). The multiplication and counting of river plancton and changes in some organisms due to formation preservation. *Public Health Repts*. 53: 2080-2093.
14. Narasimha Rao, G.M. Chatterjee, R. and Jayanthbabu, N.V. (2021). Composition and diversity of algae in Paddy fields of Razole Mandal, East Godavari district, Andhra Pradesh. *Biobrio. An International Journal of Life Science*. 6 (3&4): 411-419.
15. Nichols, H.W. and Bold, H.C. (1965). *Trichosarcina Polymorpha* gen. et. sp. nov. *J. Phycol.* 1: 34-38.
16. Pandey, J., Pandey, U. Tyagi, H.R. and Rai, N. (1998). The algal flora and Physicochemical Environment of Fath Sagar Lake. *Phykos*. 37(1&2): 29-39.
17. Prescott, G.W. (1951). *Algae of Western Great Lakes Area*. Granbrook Institute of Science 31.
18. Round, F.E. (1981). *The Ecology of Algae*. Cambridge University Press, London.
19. Sandhyarani, G. and Kumar, K.P. (2014). Distribution of Blue-green Algae in Rice-fields of Warangal District of Andhra Pradesh, India. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical Science & Research*. 4(3): 162-164.
20. Schubert, L.E. (ed.) (1984). *Algae as Ecological Indicators*, Academic Press, London.
21. Sing, R.N. (1961). Role of blue-green algae in Nitrogen Economy of Indian Agriculture, ICAR, New Delhi pp 175.
22. Singh, R., Singh, P.R. and Singh, D.V. (2015). Distribution of Cyanobacteria (Blue-green algae) in Rice-fields of Varanashi. *International Journal of Advanced Research*. 3(8): 1055 – 1060
23. Smith, G.M. (1950). *The fresh water algae of United States (Second ed.)*. Mac. Grow-Hill, New York, London.
24. Starks, T.L., Schubert, L.E. and Trainor, F.R. (1981). Ecology of soil algae. *Phycologia*. 20(1), 65-80.